

Stem cell responses to stretch and strain

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Abstract

Recent studies highlight how stem cells perceive and respond to various biomechanical cues from the extracellular niche and neighboring cells. These combined inputs drive certain stem cell behaviors, including cell fate decisions, and may influence aging and disease.

Keywords: stem cells, mechanobiology, niche, cell fate

Mechanical cues modulate SC function *in vivo*

Diverse self-renewing epithelia rely on resident stem cells (SCs) to maintain tissue homeostasis and regenerative potential. Quantitative lineage tracing, combined with advanced RNA sequencing at single-cell resolution, has revealed the dynamics and signatures of diverse tissue-specific SCs. Appropriate SC behaviors depend on their interactions with niche cells, soluble factors, and the **extracellular matrix (ECM)** (see Glossary), which have historically been investigated in biochemical and genetic terms [1]. In contrast, SC responses to mechanical cues from various components of 3-dimensional (3D) niches are largely unknown and now starting to be addressed. Here we review recent studies highlighting the influence of diverse mechanical signals (**stretch**, **strain**, and **actomyosin** contractility) on epithelial SC functions in tissue development and homeostasis *in vivo*. Understanding the forces that impact SC properties will pave the way to expand them *ex vivo*, with practical applications in regenerative medicine.

Stem cell mechanobiology

In the stratified skin epithelium, SCs reside in the basal cell layer, and their differentiated progeny fulfill barrier functions in suprabasal layers. Although SCs can respond to diverse mechanical signals, generally transmitted as forces from the actomyosin cytoskeleton, the contribution of such signals to specific SC functions *in vivo* has been unclear. In one recent study, placing a self-inflating gel under the mouse skin, mimicking a routine surgical procedure, forced localized tissue

stretch and increased the tension at cell-cell junctions [2] (Fig. 1A). This perturbation triggered SC expansion and epidermal hyperplasia, associated with nuclear localization of the mechanoresponsive transcriptional co-activator Yes-associated protein (YAP – **Box 1**) in proliferating cells [2]. Ablation of *mDia2*, an F-actin regulator, or *Myh9*, the myosin isoform involved in **mechanosensing**, impeded these effects [2], indicating that actomyosin contractility underlies the pertinent signal transmission. Since all skin layers are inter-connected through adherence to a basement membrane, the inflatable gel likely stretched all strata, thereby reducing skin cell density. Although epidermal SC proliferation could therefore be a feedback mechanism to restore cell density, stretch-induced proliferation exceeded that expectation, and the exaggerated epidermal thickness may represent an unexpected protective response [2].

In another study, expression of active forms of microtubule-severing Spastin protein or the Rho-guanine nucleotide exchange factor ARHGEF11 led to increased actomyosin contractility selectively in suprabasal cells, again increasing tension at cell-cell junctions [3] (Fig. 1B). These authors also observed epidermal SC expansion, along with reduced motility of keratinocytes and melanoblasts in the basal layer and diminished basal cell commitment into the hair follicle lineage. Pharmacologic inhibition of myosin motor activity impeded the effects, and YAP appeared in proliferating cell nuclei [3]. The seemingly similar responses to opposite perturbations of gel-induced stretching [2] and genetically enhanced contraction [3] raise interesting questions about parallel (tissue long axis) vs. perpendicular (short axis) forces in SC regulation and tissue homeostasis. For example, might horizontal SC divisions, which generate two basal daughter cells, and perpendicular divisions, which produce one basal and one suprabasal cell, result from different directions of force?

These elegant studies parallel those with physiologic mechanical strain generated at the organ level. As in the skin, basal SCs in the stratified esophageal epithelium generate differentiated cells that populate suprabasal tissue layers. Differential growth dynamics of the esophagus relative to its surrounding structures generate YAP-dependent mechanical stretch that affects the balance between the proliferation of basal cells and their exit from the cell cycle to differentiate [4]. A build-up of 20% to 40% strain was observed in the adult esophagus, and inducing this physiologic level of strain by stretching the organ in one-week-old tissue switched the SC balance from proliferation to differentiation (Fig. 1C). Conversely, increasing the strain to 100% induced proliferation [4] (Fig. 1C), similar to over-stretched epidermis [2], and pharmacologic inhibition of actomyosin contraction or YAP activity prevented these effects. Thus, **mechanotransduction** by stretching seems to depend on both developmental context and the degree of strain.

Other recent studies illustrate that mechanical forces also affect the formation of specialized SC niche structures, such as the submucosal intestinal crypts that house SCs. Crypt morphogenesis initiates during development when apical cell constriction by myosin II triggers invagination of crypt progenitor cells [5] (Fig. 1D). Examining this process in 2-D crypt organoid monolayers [6], the authors found that the SC compartment exerts pushing forces on its underlying matrix through apical constriction, while proliferative cells in adjoining hinge regions pull on the underlying substratum as they undergo basal constriction [6]. These disparate forces generate a radial gradient of increasing tension, where crypt cells drag their neighbors out of the organoid. These findings suggest that collective *in vivo* cell migration from crypts into villi may be driven by pulling forces

from villi rather than pushing forces generated by SC proliferation at the crypt base. The authors also report that soft underlying substrates (low stiffness) favored crypt morphogenesis and SC compartmentalization [6]. A parallel study with 3-D organoids and high-resolution microscopy showed similar findings, with basal villus tension coupled to crypt cell apical constriction, and changes in luminal volume by enterocytes regulating crypt morphogenesis through a mechano-osmotic mechanism [7]. These findings align with villus formation preceding crypt formation *in vivo* and may provide a framework for crypt morphogenesis.

Together, the above studies demonstrate diverse epithelial responses to mechanical forces and reaffirm the well-described role of YAP in translating those forces into biochemical signals. Deeper investigation of such experimental models will reveal additional mechanosensory and transducing factors. Other open questions include how tissues protect themselves from mechanical strain. In a recent study, physiologic and cyclic stretching applied to epidermal SCs triggered a calcium-dependent nuclear softening mediated by loss of lamina-associated heterochromatin, thereby preventing DNA damage by increasing chromosome fluidity [8]. Cell contact-mediated cytoskeletal reorganization perpendicular to the stretch then hampered this nuclear strain, allowing chromatin adaptation for long-term protection from mechanical stress [8]. While this study illuminates the importance of protective mechanisms against harmful mechanical forces, we still need to understand how cells distinguish physiologic from pathologic mechanical cues.

Beyond the pressure from hyper-proliferating cancer SCs, other biomechanical forces have been implicated in the unique architecture of early stage tumors [12]. In particular, the rigidity and rate of assembly of the basement membrane may dictate its resistance to epithelial deformation and indentation; the stiffness of differentiated cells may also play a part. Of note, elevated stiffness of differentiated cells associated with softened basement membrane enhanced tumor aggressiveness [12]. These factors may explain architectural diversity among tumor types, with further implications for normal development and maintenance of specialized epithelial structures such as intestinal crypts, hair follicles, and skin appendages.

These studies have an epithelial focus; the mechanobiology of stromal mesenchyme represents another frontier. How do fibroblast, immune, and other niche cells sense and respond to mechanical strain? A recent study reported that hair follicle SCs proliferate in response to 7 days of stretch applied with 33% strain [9]. This treatment modulated WNT and BMP pathways, with BMP-2 derived from dermal fibroblast and adipocytes while the source of WNT was not clear. Stretching also produced chemokines that attract macrophages and subsequently polarize them to the M2 type. These M2 macrophages released insulin-like (IGF1) and hepatocyte (HGF) growth factors, which activated SCs and induced hair regeneration (Fig. 1E). Although macrophage inhibition by clodronate was sufficient to impair stretch-activated hair regeneration, the precise source of chemokine signaling upon stretching and the role of mechanotransduction elements remain unknown. Future studies along these lines will reveal how mechanical strain influences ECM composition, stromal rigidity, cellular secretomes, and associated regenerative support functions. For example, although intestinal SCs seem intrinsically able to initiate crypt morphogenesis, the role of the surrounding mesenchyme and ECM remains to be investigated.

Concluding Remarks

From the practical standpoint of regenerative medicine, a better understanding of the mechanical signals that influence SCs *in vivo* could be applied to improve culture conditions for SCs *ex vivo*. For example, corneal SCs localize in a soft niche and stiffening of that corneal center induces differentiation [10]. Niche stiffness is elevated in aged hair follicles and enhanced basement membrane stiffness in young mice results in premature aging and SC exhaustion of hair follicles [11]. These observations raise the possibility that SCs generally prefer soft microenvironments.

Traditional expansion of SCs on plastic dishes with artificially high, non-physiologic stiffness can be limiting, whereas interference with mechanosensing of this extreme stiffness via PAK1-ROCK-MyosinII improves expansion of diverse epithelial SCs in 2-D cultures [13] (Fig.1 F). Likewise, gut [14] and hair follicle [15] SC organoid cultures with physiologic ECM and stiffness facilitate SC self-renewal and long-term propagation. These findings suggest that attenuating the ability to sense stiffness may bear fruit in *ex vivo* tissue expansion.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Figure 1. Schematic representation of SC responses to mechanical forces *in vivo*. Recent studies revealed that SCs can sense mechanical forces in their microenvironment and that these signals influence SC fate decision and function. (A) A self-inflating hydrogel that was transplanted underneath the skin allowed modeling the effect of stretching on skin SCs. This procedure led to enhanced SC proliferation and abnormal thickening of the epidermis. (B) Selective overexpression of Spastin or ARHGEF11 in suprabasal epidermal cells, designed to enhance actomyosin contractility in this compartment, triggered basal SC proliferation, led to abnormal epidermal thickening and reduced basal epidermal cells' commitment to hair follicle lineage. (C) During post-natal development of the esophagus, there is a need for rapid tissue expansion resulting in a physiological increase in whole organ stretching. This mechanical signal switches the balance from proliferation to differentiation of SCs, dictating epithelial thickness and resulting in the transition towards adult homeostasis. (D) Mechanical forces also affect the formation of specialized niche structures.

Apical constriction of gut epithelial SCs, mediated by myosin II, was shown to initiate the invagination and induction of crypt morphogenesis. (E) Mechanical forces also influence epithelial SCs indirectly by modulating the niche cells. Skin stretching was shown to promote chemokine production to recruit M0 macrophages that underwent polarization into M2 phenotype and released growth factors to influence hair follicle SC activation and initiate hair growth. (F) Traditional SC cultures on plastic dishes with artificially high, non-physiologic stiffness can be limiting. Recapitulating in vitro the native biomechanical properties of the niche or interference with mechanosensing of SCs will facilitate the optimized expansion of SCs in 2-D and 3-D culture conditions. Abbreviations: SC, Stem cell; ISC, Intestinal stem cell; HGF, Hepatocyte growth factor; IGF1, Insulin-like growth factor 1; 2-D, 2-dimensional; 3-D, 3-dimensional; ECM, Extracellular matrix.

Glossary

Actomyosin

The combination of cytoskeletal actin and myosin filaments that enables ATP-powered contractions and resulting force.

Extracellular Matrix (ECM)

Network of structural and functional proteins secreted by cells assembled in unique tissue-specific architectures.

Mechanosensing

The ability of cells to perceive the mechanical properties of their surroundings.

Mechanotransduction

Conversion of mechanical stimuli into biochemical signals to regulate cell behavior and function.

Stiffness

A measurement of resistance to deformation, typically represented in Pascal units.

Strain

Normalized measure of the deformation resulting from an applied force, as indicated by the normalized change in the length of the object. Strain is typically reported as a dimensionless fraction or percentage.

Stretch

Extending or spreading over an area or period of time.

Box1

The Hippo pathway

The Hippo pathway is a conserved signaling cascade first described in *Drosophila*, where the downstream effector Yorkie (YAP/TAZ ortholog) has essential roles in development, homeostasis,

and regeneration of multiple tissues. Activation of this pathway leads to phosphorylation by evolutionarily conserved kinases (MST1/2 and LATS1/2) and cytoplasmic retention of the transcriptional coactivators YAP/TAZ. Loss of Hippo pathway results in nuclear localization of YAP/TAZ and targets gene modulation. Recent studies showing cytoskeletal modulation after organ stretching [2], pulling by neighboring cells [3], and strain generated during development [4] are examples of mechanical processes that control YAP/TAZ activity *in vivo*.